

Development of the “Casanova *Drift Model*” (*CDM*)

Ed Casanova, Naresh Pai, Andrew
Chapple, Zhenglei Gao, Rena Isemer

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Why **CDM**?

// In most countries, drift **Risk Assessment (RA)** based on either Tier I drift tables or statistical models derived from data

// Very conservative buffer distances (unrealistic)

Missing component of tiered drift **RA** is publicly available, regulatory acceptable, higher tiered mathematical models

Provide conservative but realistic drift estimates

CDM has been developed explicitly for such purpose, from ground up, applicable to ground-boom based application

Two European arable crop drift models currently exist, however, all are “black boxes”

SiMod (Silsoe Spray Applications Unit, Silsoe, UK: Butler Ellis and Miller, 2010)

IDEFICS (Plant Research International, Wageningen, NL: Holterman et al, 1997)

Intent for **CDM** is to provide the model in its entirety to the public domain

Modeling Spray Drift

Model Inputs / Outputs / and Simulated Processes

	logDrift		logDrift	
Predictors	Estimates	CI (95%)	Estimates	CI (95%)
Intercept	-9.34	-10.60 – -7.95	-10.37	-11.85 – -8.93
logDist	-0.22	-0.56 – 0.11	-0.03	-0.43 – 0.35
Windspeed	0.08	-0.00 – 0.16	0.07	-0.03 – 0.16
Boom.height	4.32	3.20 – 5.39	4.17	2.89 – 5.43
Pressure	0.83	0.61 – 1.06	0.97	0.70 – 1.24
sRate	0.17	-0.09 – 0.43	0.31	0.02 – 0.59
Speed	0.17	0.09 – 0.24	0.24	0.15 – 0.32
Crop.Height	1.93	0.42 – 3.50	2.25	0.63 – 3.92
WBD	-0.03	-0.07 – 0.01	-0.02	-0.07 – 0.02
CotHeightmonocot.0M0.2	-0.96	-1.37 – -0.60	-1.02	-1.42 – -0.64
CotHeightdicot.0.2M0.4	0.13	-0.57 – 0.80	0.08	-0.58 – 0.74
CotHeightmonocot.0.2M0.4	0.47	-0.25 – 1.17	0.31	-0.44 – 1.02
CotHeightdicot.0.4M1	0.01	-0.89 – 0.88	-0.15	-1.08 – 0.74
CotHeightmonocot.0.4M1	-1.87	-3.18 – -0.67	-2.09	-3.32 – -0.81
logDist.Windspeed	0.08	0.05 – 0.11	0.07	0.04 – 0.10
logDist.Boom.height	-1.00	-1.42 – -0.58	-1.10	-1.54 – -0.66
logDist.Pressure	-0.13	-0.21 – -0.04	-0.14	-0.24 – -0.05
logDist.sRate	-0.16	-0.24 – -0.08	-0.15	-0.24 – -0.07
logDist.CotHeightmonocot.0M0.2	0.18	0.05 – 0.32	0.22	0.08 – 0.36
logDist.CotHeightdicot.0.2M0.4	-0.40	-0.55 – -0.23	-0.40	-0.55 – -0.24
logDist.CotHeightmonocot.0.2M0.4	-0.26	-0.47 – -0.06	-0.25	-0.46 – -0.05
logDist.CotHeightdicot.0.4M1	-0.34	-0.47 – -0.22	-0.34	-0.46 – -0.22
logDist.CotHeightmonocot.0.4M1	0.12	-0.09 – 0.34	0.12	-0.09 – 0.33
angle.off.ideal			-0.01	-0.02 – 0.00
logDist.angle.off.ideal			-0.00	-0.01 – -0.00
Random Effects				
σ^2	0.69		0.68	
τ_{90}	2.45		2.39	
ICC	0.22		0.22	
N	1262 _{LineG}		1182 _{LineG}	
	434 _{TrialG}		414 _{TrialG}	
Observations	9458		8659	
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.724 / 0.934		0.713 / 0.932	

Lagrangian Model Concept and DSD

Curve-fitted DSD

DSD direct from data

Includes impact of spray angle and shape from different nozzles

Wet-bulb Temperature Depression

Wind Velocity Profile

The plot below shows this profile shape taken from a paper of this subject thru a mature corn canopy ("A Mathematical Model of Air Flow in a Vegetative Canopy", Ronald M. Cionco, April 1965). The author numerically solved a differential equation to obtain this profile.

FIG. 5. A comparison of the observed wind velocities both within and above the canopy to the calculations within a mature corn canopy.

Field Segmentation: Multiple Nozzles on Boom

Fig. 2. CDM deposition for sprayed area segments. Green curves are largest droplets (>350 microns), black dashed curves are medium droplets (150 to 350 microns), and red curves are smallest droplets (<150 microns).

Fig. 3. Schematic of sprayed and drift segments simulated in the CDM. Turbulence ($\Psi\Psi\Psi$), which is based on variation in wind direction, is used to disperse the spray on drift segments.

Atmospheric Turbulence – two models provided

$$Ri = \frac{g}{T(z_1)} \frac{\left[\frac{T(z_1) - T(z_2)}{z_1 - z_2} \right]}{\left[\frac{u(z_1) - u(z_2)}{z_1 - z_2} \right]^2}$$

Table I
For Interpolation
degrees

Ri	$\psi\psi\psi$	$\Delta Y/\Delta X$
-0.860	22.50	-10.20
-0.615	20.00	-13.16
-0.235	15.00	-23.64
-0.024	10.00	-37.39
0.094	5.63	-19.24
0.236	2.88	-8.55
0.339	2.00	

If $Ri > 0$, multiply Ri by -1

$$\psi\psi\psi = k_0 * hc + k_1 * Ri$$

$k_0 \rightarrow$ 0.524 degrees/cm
 $k_1 \rightarrow$ -69.398 degrees

Eqn B

Default

avg degrees in wind direction variation, 1 sigma

Stability Class	Stability Class Definition	σ_θ	Ri
A	Very Unstable	22.50	22.5
B	Moderately Unstable	22.5	17.5
C	Slightly Unstable	17.5	12.5
D	Neutral	12.5	7.5
E	Slightly Stable	7.5	3.75
F	Moderately Stable	3.75	2.0
G	Very Stable	2.0	2.0

Simplifying Assumptions

1. DSD is identical in every streamline emanating from nozzle
2. Droplets disengage from spray liquid sheet after 10 cm – a flat liquid sheet assumed
3. Spray is broken into 3 equal flow streamlines. Recently 11 streamlines have been used with improved prediction results
4. Wet-bulb temperature depression calculated far away from spray cloud
5. Turbulence due to tractor movement is ignored
6. Tractor movement always perpendicular to wind vector profile used
7. Tractor speed and nozzle pressure / flow remain constant during application
8. End of boom closest to downwind edge of field is directly over edge of field
9. Distance between nozzle closest to downwind edge of the boom and the edge of the boom is $\frac{1}{2}$ the distance between the nozzles

Predicted / Actual Deposition Profiles

SDTF Dataset – three different nozzles (TX-6, 8004, 8004LP). Wind speed and air T measured at 4 elevations

Year of SDTF Data Collection	Terrain / Vegetation Type	Avg Vegetation Height	Number of Trials	Wind Speed Range at 6 ft (1.83 m)	°C		Avg 1 sigma variation in wind direction around mean	Richardson Number Range between 30 and 1 ft elevation
					Air Temp Range at 6 ft (1.83 m)	Range of Wet Bulb T Depression		
1992	Grass	20.32	13	8.4 to 18.3	23.4 to 33.1	2.28 to 11.79	11.0 to 27.1	-0.008 to - 0.237
1993	Grass	8.89	10	10.0 to 31.1	6.5 to 28.9	2.83 to 16.53	3.6 to 27.9	-0.015 to - 0.344

Predicted / Actual Deposition Profiles

Test against subset of SETAC EU database

- **13 total cases chosen from SETAC database (8 from Belgium, 2 from France, 2 from Netherlands, 1 from Germany)**
- Chosen cases based on ranges of controlled and uncontrolled factors
- **Ten (10) of the cases with wind speed / air temp measured at 2 elevations. Others only at 1**
- Nozzles and operating pressures – AXI11002 (1 pressure), FF11003 (3 pressures), XR11004 (2 pressures) – all nozzles considered “FINE”
- Intended Application Rate range: 1.00663 to 3.3171 kg/ha
- **Six (6) different DSD**
- Avg wind speeds from 3.4 to 15.2 km/hr
- Vegetation types – turf, grassland, fallow, and bare ground
- Canopy heights from 5 to 15 cm, with bare ground at 1 cm
- Air temp from 9.0 to 31.1 °C
- **Wet-bulb temp depression from 0.34 to 9.28 °C**
- **Boom height above canopy of 70 cm for 1 case, rest at 50 cm**
- Back-calculated tractor speed of 4.2 to 10.5 km/hr during applications

Predicted / Actual Deposition Profiles

Test against subset of SETAC EU database

- Unlike for the SDTF and Internal datasets, turbulence was not directly measured, so all the runs were evaluated with estimated turbulence from other available data. This led to conservative predictions.

CDM Predicts Higher Drift at Higher Boom Height

French SETAC Case FR_1_017

CDM Predicts Higher Far Field Drift at Higher Nozzle Pressure

Tractor Speed Doesn't Appear to Affect Drift in CDM

Conclusions

- // Very good predictive match against STDF and Internal drift tests, when all necessary factors measured
- // Preliminary comparison against selected SETAC dataset shows CDM matches relative changes in deposition profile with changes in atmospheric and geometric changes. For all cases, some parameters assumed
- // CDM assumes 100% deposition as predicted at distance, but evidence shows this changes with samplers, and is never 100%. Predicted profiles are always higher than data for EU. Efficiency of different samplers to be incorporated
- // Two turbulence models included, but vertical component of turbulence to be added
- // Wind profile changes associated with canopy height pre and post downwind field edge to be added
- // User interface being considerably improved, enabling both file upload and direct inputs for required info.
- // Objective is for R model to ultimately become **open-source code** , allowing improvements from more data from different world regions

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Thank you!

Other Slides

How Spray Drift is included in Risk Assessments

Tiered Testing

toxicity / exposure = TER > Threshold

e.g. drift value tables or simple drift models

Issue: Tiered approach to drift determination is lacking!

Solution: a higher tier mathematical model that can provide realistic estimates of spray drift of pesticides when applied to arable crops

Background

- // Model developed “from the ground up” for boom-based herbicide applications
- // Original model developed in MathCad, recently migrated to R
- // Wind speed profile $v.$ elevation includes changes in profile shape through canopy
- // Turbulence model component predicted from Richardson number, type of terrain, and canopy height using Pasquill Stability Class ranges, and another legacy model
- // Some outstanding questions:
 - // How does drop size distribution (DSD) technique affect accuracy of prediction?
 - // What is the influence of sample collection efficiency?

Surface windspeed	Daytime incoming solar radiation	Nighttime cloud cover				
		Strong	Moderate	Slight	> 50%	< 50%
< 2	< 5	A	A - B	B	E	F
2 - 3	5 - 7	A - B	B	C	E	F
3 - 5	7 - 11	B	B - C	C	D	E
5 - 6	11 - 13	C	C - D	D	D	D
> 6	> 13	C	D	D	D	D

Note: Class D applies to heavily overcast skies, at any windspeed day or night

Example of Drift Distances – from centerline of single nozzle, for one velocity profile, wet-bulb T depression of 5 °C and air T of 25 °C

Screenshots of R Version of CDM

User Guide

Data Input

Calculate

Output

Advanced

Casanova Drift Model (CDM)

[Reset Everything](#)

Choose Dataset

Choose dataset to use

Regulatory Scenarios

Select Regulatory Scenario

Select scenario

Spain

Manually Input or Edit Parameters

[Download parameters to file](#)

Environmental Settings

Dry air temperature
(Celsius):

16.80455

Barometric pressure (mmHg
abs):

722

Relative humidity (%):

33.8675

Application Settings

Density of pure water in droplet (g/cm³):

0.95

Density of dissolved solids in droplet (g/cm³):

1.915143

Mass fraction total dissolved solids in solution:

0.01881

Height of nozzle above ground (cm):

10

Intended Application Rate (kg/ha):

0.57836

Concentration in tank solution (wtfraction):

0.011305

Downwind field depth (m):

228.152

Crosswind field width (m):

748.03